

THE STUDY OF ARGOS, JARGONS AND SLANGS**Saidova Niufar Anvar qizi**Alisher Navoiy nomidagi Toshkent davlat
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The study of social dialects is one of the most actual problems of sociolinguistics. In American and European linguistics the terms argo, jargon and slang. In many languages they have their own peculiarities and are interpreted ambiguously, which indicates a wide field for the study of argot, jargon, slang and, in particular, their terminology. The issue of researching these linguistic phenomena has been topical for a long time, is an important task of modern linguistics.

In the works of foreign and domestic linguists, on which we rely, important theoretical and practical problems of studying argot, jargon and slang in American and European linguistics are considered. Theoretical and practical problems of studying argot, jargon and slang in American and European linguistics. In particular, the results of descriptive and analytical work devoted to the study of the terminology of social dialects are reflected. The works of V. A. Vinnik (2004) deserve special attention, F.Gade (1992), O.T.Gorbach (2006), M.A.Grachev (2009), D.Delaplace (2000, 2004, 2008, 2009), B.S.Istomin (2011), L.-J.Calvet (1993), J.E.Leiter (1994), A.T.Lipatov (2010), O.A.Ovchinnikova (2010), W. O'Grady (1997), T.I.Retinskaya (2012), G.V.Ryabichkina (2009), E.A.Selivanova (2008), P.A.Speirs (1991), L.A.Stavitskaya (2005), D. François-Gégère (1990), V. V.Khimik (2000), M.V.Shurupova (2012), published at the end of the XX c. - early XXI century.

D.Delaplace (2004) considers the history of the appearance of the word argos in literature, its meaning [Cited in: 19, p. 27]. J.E.Leiter (1994), R.A.Speirs (1991) in their studies reflect all those mandatory properties of slang, which distinguish it from other linguistic phenomena [Cited in: 1, pp. 45-46; 41, p. vi-vii]. M.A.Grachev (2009) considers the etymology of the word argo, the history of the use of the term argot in French [6, pp. 128-129].

Because of these studies, there is a certain theoretical result of a multidimensional study of the terminology of social dialects. At the same time, the analysis shows that for the present period the mentioned problem is not sufficiently reflected in the scientific literature.

The aim of the article is to consider the views of linguists of the 19th century - early 21st century on the issues of argot, slang and slang terminology. The aim of the study is concretised in the following tasks:

1) to make a linguohistoriographical review of the works that consider the issues of argot, jargon and slang terminology;

2) to systematise the relevant scientific achievements of foreign and domestic scientists;

3) to compare the terminology of different authors and in different languages;

4) analyse theoretical issues of terminology; 5) determine the prospects of terminology research.

The issue of terminology of social dialects is not accidentally in the field of linguists' attention. Without understanding the problems of the relevant terminology, it is impossible to make a deep study of social dialectology and its components.

The word *argo* enters the Russian language in the meaning of thieves' language in the 60s of the XIX century. It was first recorded in the Russian language in the dictionary of F. Toll (1863-1864) [18, p. 145]. In Russian science the term argot actively enters the Russian science actively in the early XX century: in the 10s - 30s of the XX century it began to be used to name secret, conditional languages identified with the "thieves'" language.

Jargon or argo (secret language) in many countries is called in different ways: in English lexicography - slang, cant, in German - rotwelsch, in Spanish - xérigonza, hermania, in Portuguese - calao, in Dutch - bargoens [10, p. 193; 27, p. 43], in French - argo, argot, etc. In Soviet linguistics, the term cant corresponded to the term argot [27, p. 43].

Originally, argot was understood as the language of the "lower classes" of society, declassified groups and the criminal world:

beggars, thieves, gambling hustlers, etc. Over time, the term argot, in addition to a narrowly specialised meaning, was given a broader meaning. J. Jordaan believes that this term, based on the circumstances, denotes:

1) the language of criminals, vagrants, beggars, etc.;

2) what is otherwise called jargon, i.e. the special language of certain social categories, for example, military, workers, students, artists, schoolchildren and others;

3) everything that penetrates into literary language from folk speech and is characterised by naturalness, spontaneity, affectivity, etc. The scientist

considers the first meaning to be the most widespread and the main one [11, p. 532].

The first two meanings of J. Jordaan coincide with the conceptual definition of the term in the Slavic tradition, but the third one diverges from it [25, p. 29]. In a narrow sense, the term argot denotes a way of communication of declassified elements, which is used in the underworld (thieves' argot), as well as the language of the people of itinerant professions, beggars, beggars.

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